

MMCs CHARACTERISATION BY INTERNAL FRICTION MEASUREMENT

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SUMMARY: The analysis of composites thermomechanical behaviour is complex considering that the deformation incompatibilities between matrix and reinforcements may be attenuated by different mechanisms.

The internal friction and the transversal elastic modulus of an Al / SiC_p composite have been measured using an experimental equipment based on sample's torsion loading in forced oscillation regime at low frequencies. The temperature was controlled and varied in the interval 90 ÷ 500 K.

Analysing the general aspect of the composite's internal friction spectrum, the peaks presence has been noticed. In the case of 6063 / SiC_p composite has appeared a transitory phenomenon of internal damping characterised by a maximum centred on the temperature of 330 K, whose intensity increased with the heating rate and the oscillation period. The phenomenon, particular for composites, has been associated to the interface presence and the dislocation saturated non-deformable zone around the reinforcements.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composites, damping, interface, dislocation, non-deformable zone.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate reinforced aluminium matrix composites are a real potential category concerning the industrial applications of MMCs. The criteria taken into account are the combination of properties, the properties isotropy, the processing possibilities and, not finally, the cost. Application of metal matrix composites in structures has been accelerated by their high specific mechanical properties and their static and dynamic stability, too. According to the references ^[1, 2, 3] metal matrix composites have both improved mechanical properties (as compared their matrix alloys) and high damping capacity, recommending them once again to be introduced in the transport field where diminution of structure vibration amplitude represents a security and comfort element.

Internal friction measurement in composites

On one hand, the experimental technique of internal friction measurement has allowed the determination of the material dynamic mechanical characteristics - transversal elastic modulus, loss factor - and their evolution when varying the testing conditions. On the other hand, the internal friction study has permitted the thoroughgoing knowledge of crystalline lattice dynamics, due to its very high sensitivity to microstructure-scaled displacements (dislocations, grain boundaries displacements, interactions between structure defects, etc.)^[4-11].

In the case of metal matrix composites, the experimental technique sensitivity to the lattice dynamics offers useful information for the complex thermomechanical behaviour and the interface characterisation. Selecting a series of the component properties of the studied composite - 6063 / SiC_p, one may point out the different and interesting behaviour of the matrix alloy and the ceramic reinforcements on three levels: different elastic behaviour, different plastic behaviour and different thermal expansion. The heterogeneous behaviour of the composite components has determined the appearance of deformation incompatibilities between the two phases during thermal and mechanical stresses. The analysis of the thermomechanical behaviour is very complex resulting that the deformation incompatibilities between matrix and reinforcements might be dissipated through different mechanisms^[9].

Taking these into account, the interface and its adjacent zone characterisation is important and necessary for the thoroughgoing study of the complex thermomechanical behaviour of the composites.

In practice, internal friction measurement is based on oscillating processes (low-frequency torsion pendulum). As a result the units of measure are oscillation quantities^[2, 3, 10] presented profitably in complex form. The complex elastic modulus is given by:

$$E^* = \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon} = \frac{\sigma_0}{\varepsilon_0} (\cos \delta + i \sin \delta) = E' + iE'' \quad (1)$$

where the real quantity represents the storage modulus : $E' = \Re E$; the imaginary quantity represents the loss modulus : $E'' = \Im E$; σ is the stress, ε the overall strain; σ_0 , ε_0 are the stress and the strain amplitudes; δ represents the loss angle by which the strain lags behind the stress when applying a time sinusoidal-varying load.

Internal friction, equal to loss tangent between applied load and resulted strain, is given by analogy with the inverse quality factor of an electric circuit, Q^{-1} . The modulus ratio represents the loss factor, respectively the internal friction:

$$\eta = \tan \delta = E''/E' = Q^{-1} \quad (2)$$

In the case of torsion loading, the relations are similar, the loss factor representing the ratio of the loss transversal modulus, G'' / storage transversal modulus, G' .

In experimental determinations of loss factor $\tan \delta$, there are obtained a number of peaks whose appearance has been determined by different physical causes, in fact different atomic-scaled processes. Loss factor dependence in function of frequency is known as internal friction (or internal damping) spectrum. Testing conditions may be varied, respectively either the frequency (using a forced vibration device) or the relaxation time, in fact the temperature at constant frequency, if relaxation time is given by an Arrhenius law.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The examined materials were 6063Al / SiC_p composites with reinforcements volume fraction of 2 %, 5% and 10 % and particles mean size of 10÷15µm. The composites were elaborated using Vortex technique, in dynamic argon atmosphere. The ceramic particles were preheated

before addition in the matrix melt. The composite slurry was poured into a steel preheated mould, then as-cast samples were homogenised and furnace cooled. Some composite samples were hot-rolled and then T6 aged (more details were given in ^[9,12]).

In this study the internal friction experiments were carried out using the equipment Micromecanalyseur - METRAVIB France. A rectangular-shaped sample (1,5x6x55 in mm) is the response element of inverted torsion pendulum, loaded in forced oscillation regime with very low amplitude. Before testing, the samples have been heat treated at 430K for 14 hours, in order to assure the results reproducibility.

The experiments had in view both the comparative study of internal friction spectrum of the analysed composites in different states - as-cast, rolled, aged - and the study of volume fraction and materials state influence on dynamic characteristics - transversal elastic modulus (Coulomb modulus), G and loss factor, $tg\delta$.

The study of loss factor variation during samples heating in the temperature interval of [90K, 500K] involved modification and control of experimental parameters, respectively: vibration frequency - 0.1Hz and 1Hz, heating rate - 35K/h and 50K/h. Oscillation amplitude, characterised by maximum strain amplitude at sample's surface, was chosen constant - 9.10^{-5} (radian), the lower amplitude determining the higher internal friction level. The sample was excited by a sinusoidal signal, in strain imposed loading mode.

Experiments involved preliminary cooling of the sample from room temperature to low limit of the testing interval, introducing the pendulum inferior part (sample and furnace) into the liquid nitrogen cryostat. Then, the experimental program was opening in order to determine the general aspect of internal friction spectrum and the transversal elastic modulus.

In order to examine microstructure, samples have been prepared using conventional metallographic technique. From the bulk specimen the samples were diamond disc cut in parallel and perpendicular direction to the rolling one, then samples were mechanically polished until 2400 grit SiC paper with very low pressure and speed. Finally, the samples were wet polished on fine velvet using chrome oxide solution, then some of them were etched with Keller reagent to evidence grain boundaries. Microstructure has been examined with the light microscope – Olympus. The porosity has been determined using arhimedic technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Damping capacity of metal matrix composites has been determined by three possible sources:

- * the matrix (effect of porosity, grain boundaries, thermoelasticity, effect of structural defects interactions, etc.);
- * the reinforcements;
- * the interfacial zone (effect of the different coefficients of thermal expansion of the components, effect of the matrix - ceramic particles interface, effect of temperature variation rate).

In the case of ceramic particles reinforced composites, both matrix and reinforcements have low damping capacity, but Al / SiC_p composites present much improved damping properties as compared the components ^[6]. The resultant enhanced damping capacity of the metal matrix composites depends not only on the intrinsic damping behaviour of individual components, but moreover on the interface-scaled behaviour and the structural modifications of the matrix due to the reinforcements presence ^[9]. Both good and poor bonding have potential for enhancing damping capacity. Well-bonded interfaces could lead to internal friction owing to increased dislocation density near interfaces, while poorly bonded interfaces could contribute to damping through a sliding friction mechanism.

The present study started from detailed research works of French colleagues ^[5, 10] on damping in aluminium alloys. Due to the expensive investigation, previous results have been used as

reference. The starting point was the internal friction spectrum of the aluminium matrix. According to references [3, 5, 10] the general aspect of internal friction spectrum of an aluminium alloy presents a very low monotonous level at low temperatures and a rapidly increase for medium temperatures (300 ÷ 430K). Spectrum increasing branch may be associated to a maximum present if the temperature continue to increase, resulting a peak centred at approximately 450K temperature, explained on the basis of inelasticity phenomena. Examining the general aspect of composites internal friction spectra (figure 1), several interesting trends may be noticed. The presence of some peaks, higher or larger in function of materials state and particles volume fraction, has been clearly associated to reinforcements influence on microstructure. Peaks appearance in low temperature interval instead of constant low fashion of the matrix alloy spectrum has been primarily attributed to interfaces and dislocation density, resulted both due to thermal stresses relaxation and material plastic deformation during secondary processing (rolling).

In order to facilitate results analysis, one overlapped different samples spectra registered during forced oscillation torsion loading. Combining in figure 1 the registrations for coded B1 - 6063Al / 10% SiC_p composite, rolled and T6 aged; coded B3 - composite containing 10% SiC_p, as-cast; coded B4 - composite with 2% SiC_p, as-cast, several trends have been remarked. In low temperature domain, transversal elastic modulus G (storage modulus) increases together with particles volume fraction and as a result of microstructure compaction through secondary processing. As temperature increase, particles volume fraction influence is diminished as well as the modulus decreases in a monotonous linear fashion (figure 1a).

Composites rolling has determined microstructure compaction revealed both by microstructure examination and porosity level measurement. Composites porosity, determined with the aid of the arhimedic technique [9], revealed a pronounced decrease from $\approx 9\%$ in as-cast state to $\approx 0.36\%$ in hot-rolled state (with the total deformation degree of 47%) [9].

Comparing the studied composites in the analysed states - as-cast and rolled, containing the particles volume fractions of 2% and 10% SiC_p, loss factor $tg\delta$ presents similar aspect with increasing tendency in all the temperature interval (figure 1b), as well as interesting features referring to the peaks.

First, considering the 10% SiC_p composites, the peaks displacement at slightly inferior temperatures is seen for rolled state in comparison to as-cast state, in accordance to processes acceleration tendency in the case of rolled composites. Taking into account that the temperature associated to internal friction spectrum peak directly depends on the activation energy for relaxation process, the 10% SiC_p composite owns a higher gradient of energy responsible for processes acceleration (recrystallization, precipitation).

Comparing the height of significant peak, the rolled composite presents a more intensive internal friction as compared to as-cast composite and this is attributed to the composite microstructure evolution during thermomechanical processing (for example, additional dislocation density and formation of the non-deformable zones). The significant peak is accompanied by a more pronounced decrease of the elastic modulus. The general aspect, slightly higher in the case of as-cast composite as compared to rolled composite (except the significant peak), may be explained either by the effect of matrix porosity or particles agglomerations associated porosity, but between these the last is more important. Next, comparing the spectra of the same state composites, for example as-cast, the displacement of 2% SiC_p composite spectrum, in comparison to 10% SiC_p composite one, indicates the major effect of interfaces and associated mechanisms. Additionally, the interesting peaks are present at same temperatures but are flattened. Examining the microstructure [9] similar porosity and grain size are seen in the case of composites containing 2%, respectively 10% SiC_p, that's why one emphasises that the higher overall level of internal friction in composites containing higher particles volume fractions is attributed to interfaces and increased dislocation density.

Fig. 1: Influence of SiC_p volume fraction and composite state on:
a) dynamic elastic modulus, G ; b) loss factor $tg\delta$, in function of temperature

Loss factor $tg\delta$ for composite constituents, as given in references, is compared to experimental data (table 1). It may be noticed the damping capacity increase of the studied composites. Although, both matrix alloy and ceramic reinforcements are materials with low damping capacity, the composite has an improved damping capacity. Unfortunately, the loss factor is still low to integrate aluminium matrix composites into high damping metals class ($tg\delta$ of order 10^{-2}), as has been stipulated at the beginning of composite research [5].

Table 1: Increase of loss factor, $tg\delta$ of 6063 / SiC_p composites

Material	Frequency, Hz	Significant peak temperature, K	Loss factor $tg\delta$ ($\times 10^{-3}$)
6061Al [2, 3, 6]	0.1÷1	450	0.8÷1.2
SiC_w (whiskers) [3]	1÷5000	-	1.1÷2.5
6063 / 2% SiC_p as -cast	0.1	365	2
6063 / 10% SiC_p rolled, T6	0.1	330	16.7
6063 / 10% SiC_p as-cast	0.1	340	6.8

Analysing in comparison the internal friction spectra of rolled composites containing different volume fractions (figure 2), it was noticed the displacement of the significant peak to lower temperature. The peak centred at approximately 330K (in the case of as-rolled 10% SiC_p composites), associated to the dislocation motion activated when temperature increase, may be explained by the superposition of thermal field and strengthening. The peak resulted higher and, in the same time, appeared sooner when the particle volume fraction increases. This fact may be explained once again by the processes acceleration with the volume fraction increase primarily due to the enhanced dislocation density. The internal friction spectrum of the 2% SiC_p composites may be considered as an intermediately case between the matrix alloy and the composites containing current volume fractions.

Fig. 2: Loss factor variation in function of temperature for as-rolled composites

Analysing testing conditions influence in the case of rolled and T6-aged composite (10% SiC_p) - figure 3, particular aspects in comparison to alloys are noticed. Transversal elastic modulus decreases more at higher heating rate (figure 3a). Although not reported, same tendency is noticed for as-cast composites. All temperature interval and especially for medium temperatures, the increase of temperature variation rate determines loss factor increase, the

peak of interest being more evident for higher heating rates (figure 3b). In the case of matrix alloy, heating rate modification does not imply the sensitive variation of internal friction spectrum^[10] and that's why this aspect, specific to composites, is associated to reinforcements presence.

Fig. 3: Influence of testing parameters - heating rate, T and frequency, f on: a) dynamic elastic modulus, G ; b) loss factor $\text{tg}\delta$, in function of temperature

Moreover, oscillation frequency influence is important remarking that for frequencies exceeding 1Hz internal friction spectrum becomes monotonous and the peak is not recorded. Comparing again with the matrix alloy ^[10], frequency effect as well as temperature variation rate one, are particular features for composites.

The dependence of internal friction on heating rate and oscillation frequency may find an explanation in the heterogeneous behaviour of composite components. Internal friction is related both to the relaxation strains in the matrix and interface phenomena. It should be noted that if the strain is not constrained, the motion of dislocations does not produce an internal friction effect.

This series of experiments allowed emphasising qualitative information on composites internal friction and its correlation with their particular thermomechanical behaviour.

Examining microstructure of as-cast (figure 4) and rolled (figure 5) composites, the tendency of particle alignment in the rolling direction has been emphasised. Detailed examination of microstructure has revealed the matrix yielding perturbation by the reinforcements and the formation of a non-deformable zone adjacent to the particles. The particle adjacent matrix layer is rapidly saturated in dislocations due to the high residual stresses at the interface level. This layer together with the particle act as rigid obstacle for matrix yielding, resulting a lenticular-shaped distortion of the sliding planes and crystalline grains around the reinforcements (fig. 6). These non-deformable zones saturated in dislocations may be considered responsible for the internal friction phenomenon in particulate reinforced aluminium matrix composites.

CONCLUSION

1. Experimental technique of internal friction registration presents high sensitivity at microscopic-scaled displacements in materials. For this reason the technique is perfectly adapted for the study of ceramic particles reinforced metal matrix composites whose specific behaviour at thermal and mechanical stresses is determined by microstructure evolution and complex phenomena associated to interface.
2. Although the composites constituents are materials (metallic alloy, ceramic) with low damping capacity, composites internal friction, in terms of loss factor, increases due to the interface-scaled behaviour and interaction mechanisms between matrix and reinforcements.
3. Internal friction spectra of the composites present higher or larger peaks in function of the material state and the particles volume fraction. The peaks appearance is associated to the interface and the enhanced dislocation density due to reinforcements presence and material secondary processing.
4. At low temperatures the transversal elastic modulus increases together with particles volume fraction and as a result of secondary processing. Temperature increase leads to particles volume fraction influence diminution and modulus decrease in linear fashion.
5. The significant peak is higher and appears sooner in the case of higher particles volume fraction, therefore pointing out the processes acceleration tendency in composites.
6. The internal friction phenomenon is characterised by the peak centred at approximately 330K and its intensity increases with the heating rate and the oscillation period. The effects of temperature variation rate and oscillation period are particular to composites.

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Fig. 4: Microstructure of as-cast 6063 / 10% SiC_p composite

Fig. 5: Microstructure of rolled 6063 / 10% SiC_p composite

Fig. 6: Non-deformable zone and lenticular-shaped distortion adjacent to ceramic particles

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